

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OFORI-KOREE****FIRST NAME: NANA YAA****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did not use Zotero to insert references

The author did not use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MS Word 365

THE BASICS TO GOOD ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

ACA-401D period one (1) serves as the basis for the entire doctoral course by providing the reader with several tools and techniques to set them up to become a good academic writer. These include determining the purpose of the academic paper, understanding the essay planning process, ensuring a logical flow of thoughts, acknowledging sources of information, writing in the appropriate style, and using good grammar.

Authors L. Cleenewerck and K. Gulma provide the student with relevant information in a publication organised into nine (9) chapters. Chapter one (1) provides the basics and purpose of essay writing; Chapter two (2) focuses on the integrity of the writer by addressing plagiarism and appropriate citing. Chapters three (3) and four (4) delve into the proper use of grammar by authors; whilst Chapter five (5) covers the different styles with a focus on the recommended style for EUCLID students, that is, Turabian. The topic of style and grammar continues in Chapter six (6), albeit from a different angle, that is, the differences between Standard American English and Standard British English.

A sample of a reviewed paper is included in Chapter seven (7) to enable the reader to see a practical example of good academic writing. Examples of good academic papers are also included in the general orientation pack, and all these are intended to give the student a good understanding of what is expected throughout the doctoral journey. The crib sheet in Chapter eight (8) lends itself as an easy to use reference guide to ensure that the papers are written in the correct style; with the final chapter (9), providing more information on grammar, particularly, the use of Latin expressions and abbreviations.

An additional resource is provided in the form of a video delivered by L. Cleenewerck, which focuses on how the student is expected to edit the EUCLID response paper template.

2) INSIGHTS

Returning to formal education after a hiatus can be a daunting task for most people, and I am no exception. Therefore, I expected my first paper to re-introduce me into academia, whilst allowing me to unlearn, learn and re-learn the accepted approach to academic writing. This paper was great in doing that by presenting the key concepts required for me to develop and write a good paper. However, I also recognise that to write a great paper I would need to do two (2) key things- practice academic writing regularly and conduct more personal research into good academic writing.

I made several observations in the publication, which challenged me to consider and reflect on whether I was truly examining the paper critically or it was a lack of familiarity with the topic under discussion.

Of key concern to me is that, in as much as the publication intends to provide the learner with the required basic information on academic writing, the document reads like a compendium of information as opposed to one single coherent source of information. The use of different font styles used in each chapter also did not make for easy reading.

The insertion of the section titled 'Basic steps in writing an essay', which is a summary of the steps in essay writing, on the first page seems misplaced. The logical approach is usually to have a summary placed at the end of documents after the reader has had the opportunity to gain an initial understanding of the topic under discussion. With the summary section placed at the beginning of the document, this opportunity has been involuntarily taken away from the reader. This goes further to defeat any attempt to provide the reader with a logical flow of information. My suggestion is that it should be replaced with the section on 'Tips for effective writing' (EUCLID 2019, 3) and the 'Basic steps in writing an essay' introduced later in the chapter, once the reader is more comfortable with the topic under discussion.

My most recent experience with citing is from my graduate studies in Health, Development and Environment, where we used the Harvard referencing style. I was keen to explore the similarities and/or differences with the Turabian style. In reading the course material, I find the recommendations on when not to cite interesting, particularly the advice relating citing with regards to topics about which the writer may be a novice at. The advice is to not cite when the information is "repeated in many different sources"; in which case the writer is to assume it is "common knowledge" (EUCLID 2019, 10). I am curious to understand how to define "many different sources", and expect that with further writing experience, I would find clarity on this. My previous knowledge of citing online works is for one to include the day the website was accessed; however, I do not see this as part of the format detailed in the EUCLID document (EUCLID 2019, 11). In citing Gerson and Gerson on page eleven (11), there is no comma between the authors and the page number.

This is also repeated on the next page contrary to the Turabian in-text style of citing. The eleven (11) important reminders for literature reviews (EUCLID 2019, 17) appear to be important, however, they are presented without any context making it difficult for me to understand. My preference would have been for a more practical explanation by providing examples for each reminder.

3) BEGIN WITH THE END IN MIND

Authoring a good academic paper requires that I effectively engage my reader by delivering a persuasive and convincing argument; this is my purpose as a good writer (EUCLID 2019, 1 - 4). This can only be done by planning and preparation; very much like the steps required to implement a good project. A significant portion of my career revolves around project management, where the basic steps include planning/preparation, acting/doing, reviewing/improving. This is very much aligned to the steps required to author academic papers, that is, the methodical and logical approach to structuring, preparing, researching, writing, and submitting an academic paper. When I assess the seven overarching steps and guidance to authoring an academic paper, it is easy to see the logical flow, further making it easy for me to use as a quick guide throughout the doctorate.

The use of an essay plan is useful in structuring the essay and guides the writer to research the topic of discussion. However, I accept that have to remind myself to have an open mind, be flexible and open to revising this essay plan depending on the research findings, because it is only through the research process that I can analyse varying views and deliver my argument. By critically analysing the writing process from start to end, I see that the practice of writing is a continuous learning process. All the steps the author takes to produce a good academic paper requires that he or she be mentally focused, always keeping the purpose of the essay in mind. Reading very widely is a key feature of lifelong learning and will be a key feature of my academic journey. By reading widely and critically analysing various publications, the author is increasing their knowledge and scope of understanding of a topic. This, to me, is a hallmark of not only a good author but a great scholar.

One of the challenges that I would have to constantly address is passive writing. Writing with a passive voice is my style and I would have to make a conscious effort to avoid that. I believe the suggestion to get other people to review my essays including reading them out loud will help address this issue (EUCLID 2019, 16).

I have always considered plagiarism as a moral and ethical issue. I view plagiarism as not only restricted to academic writing but is evident in everyday publications especially in this era of social media and self-aggrandizement, where the moral fabric of society is threatened by the ambition for individuals to be liked. As studying doctorate level focuses on the ability to conduct independent research, analyse, challenge and validate varying points of view and advance critical thinking; in most cases to develop new theories and ideas, it is very disingenuous for a writer to plagiarise information. Apart from the ethical and moral considerations at hand, it also invalidates/ does not acknowledge the work and effort that the original writer/researcher would have put into their craft.

In my view, plagiarism is a deliberate theft of ideas which can be easily avoided by following the approved approach to citing publications.

4) CHALLENGE YOUR THINKING

This is a central concept for all academic essays and is often a complex thing to do. As individuals with years of life's experiences, belief systems and professional knowledge, we are often set in our thinking. The art and science of accepting what one knows, whilst recognizing the need to assess and objectively analyse other viewpoints is key to being a good doctoral student. I am glad this topic has been introduced during the first period of the course, as it will help me mentally prepare for the academic journey. A good academic writer must identify what he/she knows and recognise that there is more information required to make an argument based on creative and critical thinking.

Reading with a purpose is a learning process for the writer (EUCLID 2019, 2). By reading widely but purposefully, assessing the relevance of the documents, using it to challenge or support the thesis of the essay is one of the distinct features of an academic essay. This suggested a structured approach to researching is also especially useful in helping me develop my ideas.

5) TOMATO, TOMATOE

Consistency in my style of writing is important if I want to succeed as a doctoral student and academic. I understand the need to use an approved style, as I recognise the purpose of having a set approach to the style and delivery of my work. Using appropriate style when writing is very similar to an organisation having branding guidelines which determine the style, messaging, and format of official engagements between an organisation and its stakeholders. As part of my career, I have led many public relations and communication activities, for which I am mandated to use approved branding guidelines. These branding guidelines provide details on how the organisation uses font styles, colour pantones, use of logos, positioning of logos, key institutional messages, etc. The need for a writing style reminds me of these branding guidelines and the need to adhere to them.

The advice to let your ear be your guide supports similar advice in the previous section, where the writer is advised to read out their draft work out loud (EUCLID 2019, 21).

Throughout my academic journey, I have used Standard British English (SBE), therefore, I am relieved that it is not mandatory to use Standard American English (SAE) in my scripts. The examples provided in the text with regards to spellings, pronunciations, grammar, expressions, and general usage makes me wonder how the language will evolve into the future. Given the technological advances since the Turabian was written, I find the advice on the paper type to be used for publications quite outdated (EUCLID 2019, 55).

I am a visual learner and learn by doing. Therefore, it is no surprise that I particularly enjoyed reading the sample of the edited academic paper (EUCLID 2019, 36 – 43) as well as the video on how to edit an academic paper to adhere to the EUCLID style for response papers. These were the most important resources for me, as I prefer practice to theory. By examining the corrections made to the sample paper, I am better able to understand the guidelines, techniques, styles which are described in the preceding chapters. The corrections made, appear to be common sense, however from my experience, no matter how skilled an author is, there are bound to be some mistakes in the essay. The purpose of the corrections is also very clear, that is, to improve the writing style, grammar, enforce logical flow, cite appropriately, and present convincing content to the reader- all the attributes of a well written academic paper.

The process of writing this response paper is also enabling me to reflect on the resources I have reviewed, practice what I have learnt and I expect that my academic paper writing skills will only get better with time.

6) CONCLUSION

My initial reaction after reading the table of contents was that period one (1) is very reminiscent of my first course during my undergraduate studies, ‘Communication Skills 101’. Has this module revived the same feelings as my communications course during my undergraduate degree did? Absolutely yes. I feel the same way, excited, apprehensive, and positive that I have made a particularly excellent choice in starting this PhD.

Reading, analysing, and writing are the fundamentals of a doctorate thus making this module a good starting point for a new student. I thoroughly enjoyed getting exposed to a superior way of writing, with a full understanding that it would set the foundation for the success or otherwise of my studies. By writing a response paper immediately after studying this module, I can put into practice what I have learnt. As I previously mentioned, I learn by doing, therefore this is a useful way to ensure that I understand what I have studied.

I found it especially useful to understand what an academic essay is, in contrast to other forms of writing that I am used to, i.e., business writing and social writing. My expectations as I started studying the material was that there will be significant similarities between business and academic writing, albeit with differences based on the audience for the document and purpose of the essay. This was confirmed, as I noted that the similarities lie in the need for both types of documents to deliver a persuasive argument using appropriate grammar and in line with the agreed style of the organisation. The key differences revolve around the academic paper requiring me to challenge my established views on a topic, by reading and analysing a wide range of publications, citing, and adhering to the academic style of writing. Per the cliched phrase, ‘Practice makes perfect’ and I expect that my writing will get better as I progress along with this doctorate.

REFERENCES

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